
Intellectual Property Rights in Digital Mahila Bachat Gat Women Entrepreneurship

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DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.14905023

Abstract:

"Mahila Bachat Gazrt" is one of such measures which come under Self Help Group and which is responsible for Social and Economic development of Women specifically of illiterate and economically poor groups. Maharashtra Region belongs to Population of Women of Socially and Economically backward category to which Mahila Bachat Gat helped for empowerment. IP rights are enshrined in Article 27 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights of 1948. Only 16 percent of patent applications are filed from women, the remaining is from men. There are certain problems faced by women in protecting IP rights. Some of them are Gender bias, financial constraints, Lack of IP education and awareness, Lack of representation. These challenges need efforts for promoting gender equality and also inclusiveness in the field of IP. The practice of IP law and management is its own profession for the reason it requires specialized training. Most of the creations and ideas made by women are not protected under the category of intellectual property for the main reason, of long procedures involved and also unaware of the legal side of IP. Closing the gender gap in IP requires empowering women through education, mentor-ship and support.

Keyword: Digital Bachat Gat, Intellectual Property Rights, Women Empowerment.

Introduction:

Intellectual property Rights, even though constitute the intangible fraction of rights available to any individual, institution or business concern, are one of the most important and economically viable rights in the present day. The ambit of intellectual property rights may include a plethora of dimensions such as ideas of entrepreneurs, inventions, artistic creations, literary works, etc., and are available in the forms of patents, trademarks, and copyrights. One of the growing and rising shares of authors, entrepreneurs, business owners and technical developers globally in the recent past have been women who have entered into a plethora of fields and have contributed

significantly to innovations in these fields Women entrepreneurs half of the population of mankind yet the condition of women in today society is miserable. The economic and social development not yet satisfactory growth. The vital role of women entrepreneur in Indian economic development. Innovation and risk taking are important functions of women entrepreneurs. Mahila Bachat Gat is one of calculates which come under self Help Group which is social economic development. Mahila bachat Gat is team work includes poor women come together and try to poverty reduction and try too independent. The majority women of socially and economically backward

category to which Mahila Bachat Gat helped for women empowerment in Maharashtra state. The main object of focus to expand a website that digital commerce.

Objective of the Study:

1. To study the need of IPR digital Mahila Bachat Gat.
2. To study the advantages of IPR digital Mahila Bachat Gat.
3. To study the problems and solutions of IPR digital Bachat Gat

Research Methodology:

The main objective of this paper is to understand the progress of the IPR digital Mahila Bachat Gat of self-help groups concerning the various projects in different states. It also covers the impact of such initiatives and also provides some policy suggestions for better inclusion. The study is IPR women empowerment descriptive and based on the data available for financial inclusion and self-help groups in the reports published by the National Bank for Agricultural and Rural Development, Reserve Bank of India, etc. various studies were undertaken by different scholars in this area have been analyzed to their findings are placed in the research paper mainly depend on secondary data i.e. data available from following sources for the purpose of research study. Research paper, books and journals, seminars paper, internet website etc. this paper.

Need of the Study:

Bachat gat Software is available in online platform. Here we have various modules that make it perfect software for bachat gat. We have developed bachat gat software in very simple and user-friendly environment that can help in accounting all your needs in this software. Self Help Groups (SHGs) have emerged as working platforms for empowering women, creating self-reliant decision-makers, and managing

entrepreneurial businesses for sustainable income-generating activities, thereby contributing to socioeconomic advancement. SHGs in India have been instrumental in innovatively weaving traditional knowledge and wisdom with current ethos and societal demands servicing all sectors spanning from household necessities, foods, fashion, media, telecommunication, healthcare, etc. Economic Survey 2022-23 has made a special mention of SHGs in India during the Covid-19 crisis leading from the front in producing masks (with cultural variants such as Gamusa Masks in Assam), sanitizers, and protective gear, creating awareness about the pandemic (e.g. Patrakar Didis of Jharkhand), delivering essential goods (e.g. Floating supermarkets in Kerala), running community kitchens (e.g. Prerna Canteens in Uttar Pradesh), supporting farm livelihoods (e.g. Pashu Sakhis for animal health care services, Aajeevika Farm Fresh Online selling and distribution mechanism for vegetables in Jharkhand), convergence with MGNREGS (in UP, Bihar, Chhattisgarh), and in delivery of financial services (e.g. Bank Sakhis managing bank rush for availing Covid-relief DBT cash transfers).

IPR problems of Women Entrepreneurship:

- 1) **The practice of IP law and management-** The own profession for the reason it requires specialized training. Most of the creations and ideas made by women are not protected under the category of intellectual property for the main reason, of long procedures involved and also unaware of the legal side of IP.
- 2) **Closing the gender gap-in IP** requires empowering women through education, mentor-ship and support. The purpose of IP rights is to encourage and develop innovation and creativity, which in turns helps

to improve the quality of our lives. Women may face difficulties in understanding the intricacies of IP laws, filing applications or in enforcing their rights

- 3) **Limitations on women's** -legal capacity cause a burden on their decision-making ability. Striking a balance between work and home is important not only for women but also an equal responsibility of men. For decreasing the gender gap, it is mandatory to create an inclusive environment. The World Intellectual Property Day, observed on April 26, was this year dedicated to women the challenges women inventors, authors and creators face in entering innovative fields and sustaining themselves. Gender plays a role in who claims and exercises intellectual property — which exists in the market as patents, copyrights and trademarks. Data shows very few women are participating in the intellectual property system; and subsequently, very few women are benefitting from it.
- 4) The World Intellectual Property Day, observed on April 26, was this year dedicated to women like Lamarr. Supreme Court judge Justice Hima Kohli in a public address spoke about the challenges women inventors, authors and creators face in entering innovative fields and sustaining themselves. Gender plays a role in who claims and exercises intellectual property — which exists in the market as patents, copyrights and trademarks. Data shows very few women are participating in the intellectual property system; and subsequently, very few women are benefitting from it.

- 5) The American inventor (and famed Hollywood actor) developed a frequency-hopping technology that would one day spawn wireless communication tech in the form of Bluetooth, GPS and Wi-Fi. Still, Lamarr didn't receive credit for her invention for decades. Never in her lifetime did she earn money for a technology she pioneered.

IPR Solutions of Women Entrepreneurship:

Women participation can be increased in the IPR field by incorporating certain steps, few of which are:

- 1) **Awareness and Outreach:** By organizing workshops, seminars, and conferences that highlight the contributions of women in the IPR field can significantly aid women in knowing the various dimensions of this field. These events can also serve as networking opportunities.
- 2) **Networking and Professional Associations:** By supporting the creation of women-focused or diversity-focused IPR professional organizations and encouraging participation in existing associations.
- 3) **Equal Opportunities in Employment:** By promoting equal opportunities and pay equity for women in the workplace, including within law firms, corporate legal departments, and government agencies dealing with IPR.
- 4) **Support for Entrepreneurs and Startups:** By Providing funds, mentorship, and resources specifically tailored to the needs of women entrepreneurs and inventors in the IPR field.
- 5) **Policy Advocacy:** By advocating for policies that promote gender diversity in IPR, both at the national and international levels, also by

encouraging Government to collect and publish data on gender diversity in IPR-related industries.

Programs for Women Entrepreneurs Empowerment:

Other interventions target women. For women in lower-income areas or developing countries who lack access to quality education, a series of training workshops can be provided to educate them and encourage them to enter innovative fields. Laboratorial, an organization founded by a female entrepreneur, provides “boot camps” for women across Latin America to learn the skills necessary for tech careers. Over three years, more than 1,000 women graduated from Laboratorial, and 80 per cent of the 2017 class went on to work in the industry. In Mexico, a program called Victoria 147 provides a platform for training, incubation, acceleration and networking that focuses on the development and empowerment of female entrepreneurs and executives in Mexico. With offices in Mexico City, Merida and Monterrey, Victoria 147 is the largest and most experienced organization in Mexico offering training and networking opportunities for businesswomen. In Japan, the Government launched the “Creating a Society in Which All Women From 2002 to 2018, approximately 600 women were trained by the program. Of these, 150 are now qualified patent agents. More than 60 per cent of the women are now gainfully employed. A number of them are self-employed. The three-part WOS initiative addresses the lack of training and resources head-on by providing resources aimed specifically at enabling women innovators to learn and grow professionally. WOS-C is also aimed at addressing the lack of qualified women in IP law and administration roles, as well as the discrepancy in the awareness of women entrepreneurs of the relevance and value of IPRs to their careers. In addition, WOS-A

and WOS-B both offer opportunities for women to advance in IP-intensive fields. This initiative therefore works to solve four of the five IP gender gap challenges presented in this paper end Shine” program,

Conclusion:

This project would be very useful to them for selling their product of different categories using filters and also publishing their Bachat Gat products wherever they want. Due to the Bachat Gat's traditional method of product publication in the current system, we are creating an online shopping website for them. so that they can publish a variety of products on this website and attract more customers. They may sell their products in many categories utilizing filters and publish their Bachat Gat products virtually anywhere. In existing system, the Mahila Bachat Gat having their own traditional way of publishing their product through this project we are introducing online shopping website for them. The report highlights the scheme, functioning, and the impact created by the major initiatives of the Government of India. The report primarily focuses on three types of initiatives – Awareness, capacity building in science and technology, and Career Re-tracking for Women. The report further demonstrates steps taken to accelerate professional development in innovation and IPR and increase in women’s involvement in science and technology. The NIPAM initiative aims to create awareness about IPR which has a staggering reach of total beneficiaries going over 2 million, of whom more than 1 million are women.

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